

TREATMENT OF VARIOUS PSYCHOLOGICAL CHANGES MANIFESTED IN PRESCHOOL CHILDREN THROUGH "FAIRY TALE THERAPY".

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Scientific and theoretical study of psychological characteristics of preschool children is of great practical importance in higher pedagogical education.

That is why psychological changes in preschool children are one of the important factors affecting the development of society. When a child reaches school age, serious changes occur in his mental development. The reason is that it is from this period that the child's independent activity expands. At the same time, anxiety, fear, lack of communication skills, and inability to get along with peers begin to appear. One of the effective ways to overcome these changes is "Fairy tale therapy".

Fairy tale therapy is a method of psychological support and development, a method of education and treatment aimed at exploring and solving the child's inner world, feelings and problems through fairy tales. Through this method, children can see and understand themselves or their situation through the characters of fairy tales. Fairytale therapy has many advantages in learning and developing the child's inner world.

The use of fairy tale therapy allows us to:

- ✓ Effectively helps in emotional expression and understanding, reducing stress and tension. The reason is that through this method, children can easily express their frustrations and fears. This will reduce their stress and improve their mood.
- ✓ At the same time, fairy tale therapy helps to develop imagination and creativity in children, increase self-confidence, improve communication skills, and develop self-awareness. Through fairy tales, children acquire new skills in communicating with others and expressing themselves.

Not using fairy tale therapy means losing opportunities for self-development and emotional support for children. If this therapy is not used, it can lead to difficulties in understanding problems, increased stress and emotional burden, reduced ability to develop creativity and imagination, decreased self-confidence, limited communication skills, inability to approach difficulties artistically, and slowed down self-awareness. we can observe.

Bruno Bettelheim, a famous psychoanalyst and child psychology researcher in the United States, conducted a study on fairy tale therapy. He has conducted several studies on the positive effect of fairy tales on the psyche of children. Her book *The Uses of Enchantment* discusses how fairy tales can help children overcome their fears and anxieties. Bettelheim's research has shown that fairy tales help children to understand their inner feelings.

In Switzerland, the famous psychoanalyst Carl Jung and his followers studied fairy tales in relation to the human psyche and explored their archetypal (ancient symbolic) nature. He and his followers did a lot of research on the influence of fairy tales on the inner world and

development of a person . They noted that fairy tale therapy is an effective way to work with a person's subconscious.

Salvador Minuchin, another well-known specialist in family therapy from the USA, noted that fairy tales can be used to improve communication between family members. Her research has explored ways to solve family problems through storytelling and has shown that this approach is effective in overcoming family problems.

In Uzbekistan, psychologists and pedagogues have learned and are trying to apply the method of fairy tale therapy, but this direction is still at the stage of development. Some local psychologists and teachers have used this method in working with children and received positive results. An example of them is Dilfuza Fayziyeva, an Uzbek psychologist. Having studied the methods of using fairy tale therapy in preschool educational institutions, he found that it has a positive effect on the mental development of children. His research shows that through stories, children can better understand their feelings, improve their self-explanatory skills, and develop their imagination.

Research centers in Tashkent and other major cities are also studying fairy tale therapy as a method of psychological support for children and families. Studies have shown that story therapy is beneficial in reducing children's fears and anxieties, as well as increasing self-confidence. In the research conducted by some local psychologists of the State Institute of Psychology of Uzbekistan, they developed a manual and methodical recommendations for teachers and psychologists using fairy tale therapy. Their results showed that story therapy can facilitate learning, reduce stress and develop social skills for children.

Tale therapy as a result of research conducted abroad and in Uzbekistan

- Reducing stress and anxiety in children
- To improve emotional expression and self-awareness
- To increase the ability of creative and logical thinking
- to increase self-confidence

- It has been found to have a positive effect on improving family communication and solving family problems with a light approach.

Including, based on the results of our own observation and research, we can say that fairy tale therapy has a positive effect on children, and indeed, one of the most pressing problems today is the lack of communication skills, fear and anxiety in children. we should emphasize that it is one of the effective ways to eliminate psychological problems that arise in children due to the high level.

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